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Societal and Social Media as Contributing Factors to Parental Failure in this Age of Perfectionism

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Abstract

The study examines societal and social media factors contributions to parental failure in the contemporary age of perfectionism. Discussion is focused on how societal expectations, norms, values, and social media spreads have created an environment where parents feel pressured to be perfect leading to increased anxiety, guilt and shame. It articulates the societal and social media factors that contribute to the phenomenon of parental failure in the age of perfectionism. The study also discusses parents' perceptions of their own competence and worth, the roles of social media advancement play in perpetuating the idea of a perfect parent. The study highlights the need for a paradigm shift in societal expectations and social media ideologies surrounding perfection in parenting. Having identify that, perfect parenting is unrealistic, recommendation is placed on creating a more supportive and inclusive environment for parents. Parents should accept uncertainty, practice self-compassion, embrace mindfulness and set realistic and flexible goals in their parenting practices.

Keywords: Parental failure, perfectionism, Mental Health and social media.

Introduction

There has been a growing concern in recent years about the rising expectations and pressures placed on parents to be perfect. This phenomenon has been referred to as the age of perfectionism (Hewlett & Nest, 1998). Perfectionism in parenting refers to the expectation that parents should be flawless, selfless, and completely devoted to their children needs (Furreddi, 2002). The Cultural and societal factors contributing to this phenomenon are complex and multifaceted. Social media platforms, such as instagram and Facebook have created a culture of Curated perfection, where parents feel pressured to present a flawless image of their family (Kapla & Haelem, 2010). The major contribution to the idealisation of perfect parenting celebrity parenting and media representation. (Douglas & Michaels, 2004)

A sense of anxiety and uncertainty among parents who feels they must follow a set of rigid rules and guidelines in order to be good parent given birth to by the rise of expert parenting advice and the proliferation of parenting books and blogs (Farcloth, 2013).

Parental failure, or the perception of failure can have severe and bring lasting consequences for parent mental health and well-being, as well as on parent-child relationships and child development (Hinkley & Taylor, 2012). The pressure to be perfect can lead to feelings of guilt, shame and inadequacy among parents, who may feel that they are failing to meet the expectations placed upon them (Tardy, 2000).

Parents who feel they have failed may experience increased stress and anxiety, which can negatively impact their mental and physical health (Hinkley of Taylor, 2012) Parental failure can lead to decreased self-esteem and confidence, making it more difficult for parents to effectually care for their children (Tardy, 2000). Parent-child relationship can be damaged by parental failure, and leading to increased conflict and decreased warmth and responsiveness (Shankoff & Philips, 2000). Negative outcomes may be experienced by children whose parent feel they have failed. It will have a devastating effect on their academic achievement, social skills, and emotional well-being. Presumed parental failure can increase the work of mental problems including depression anxiety, and substance abuse, in both parents and children (Neissman, 2018).

Perfectionism in parenting involves parent's constant showing for flawless parenting, setting extremely high standards for themselves and the children, and often experiencing excessive self-criticism. This can manifest as "should" mindset, where parents compare themselves to unrealistic ideals and societal expectations. It is a belief that anything less than perfect is unacceptable, and a tendency to micromanage or pressure children to succeed. In reality perfection is nothing but an illusion, but when it comes to parenting, perfect seems to be the goal to aim for. If this is what we are aiming at, it is an

illusion, we are all doomed to fail; yet, the quest for perfection is rooted in the desperate desire to avoid failure. Thus, we enter a vicious of expectation and aims to set too high, leading to unavoidable failure, leading to guilt, depression and dented self-esteem and confidence, causing us to once again assess our parenting skills and aim for the fallacy of perfect. It is a toxic, debilitating, cycle that must be break if we hope to succeed as a parent.

Social media and Perfectionism

Today's world is one where events and achievements big and small, and adventures are on display on Instagram, Tik Tok, Facebook, or twitter. It is a daily barrage of polished vacation photos, perfectly posed selfies, witty videos, and foodie approved plates. Social media has gifted the world with empowering movements and the voice of guilty, but it has also contributed to increased feeling of depression, bullying, and more. While these networks can be fun and engaging way to get news updates, and stay in touch with family and friends, they encourage comparism, often through the number of likes post received. In addition, social media has equally been shown to negatively impact mental health especially for teens. Posts, likes, and comments can contribute to feelings of perfectionism and anxiety negatively.

The Social Media (SM) pressure to do better can manifest as an intense drive for illusory flawlessness and stringent self-evaluation personality characteristics referred to as perfectionism (Hewitt & Flet, 1991) Perfectionism represents a tormenting way of going through life. Evidence of the danger posed by the pressure to be flawless on social media can be found, for example, in the risks taken to create posts. Users have been caught having photo session in fake private jet studios (Lim, 2023). In one extravagant rented locations (eg Huddleston, 2021) and engaging in dangerous activities (Turel, 2021). In one extreme case, the desire for a perfect selfie resulted in an attempted suicide. I was constantly need in search of taking The perfect selfie and when I realised I couldn't, I wanted to die. It becomes a mission to get approval and it can destroy anyone. (Dany Bowman as cited In Griffiths & Balakrishnan, 2016)

Given the risk pose by the SM pressure to be flawless, Information systems research needs to realise a better understanding of users' perfectionistic tendencies in this specific context and their implications for user behaviour and system design. Research has focused more on concepts such as social comparison and envy Κλάσηους, Widjala, Buxmang, Wenninger & Breibasat, 2015; Meylhaber, Krause, Baumann, Krasnova & Thatcher, 2013) to study how users benchmark themselves and infer their relative standing on SM. However, social media perfectionism represents more than just the tendency to benchmark and self-evaluate. It also reflects the drive to act upon-mostly unfavourable-self-evaluations. For instance evidence of "snapchat dysmorphia" (Rajanala, Maymode, Vashi, 2018) and "Instagram face" (Tolentino, 2019), suggests that the need to perfect oneself may not only stem from other users' looks, and performance but could be a direct consequence of technology itself. Social media filters enable comparing ones real self to a digitally enhanced "perfect" version.

The Societal Factors Contributing to perfectionism in Parenting

Societal expectations is also instrumental in shaping parental beliefs and behaviour, influencing how parents raise their children and perceive their role as caregivers. Societal expectations around gender roles continue to influence parenting, with father often expected to be breadwinners and mothers expected to be primary caregivers. It also promote specific parenting Styles, such as helicopter or attachment parenting which can lead to feelings of guilt or inadequacy on the part of the parents.

Societal expectations around academic achievement can lead parents to priotize grades over emotional well-being, contributing to students stress and anxiety (Kohn, 2020). Cultural norms and values shape parental beliefs and behaviour, with variations across culture Societal expectations and economic success can lead parents to priotise material security over emotional connection with their children. This symptom can contribute to parental stress, anxiety and depression, impacting mental health and well-being. Expectation of the society can impact parenting confidence, with parents feeling inadequate if they don't meet certain standards, Understanding societal expectations affects parental beliefs and behaviour can inform policy initiative supporting diverse family structures and promoting inclusive parenting practices.

Economic crises can cause parents to worry about their children future and can lead to stress and anxiety. Financial struggles can cause parents to feel stressed and anxious about how they are going to provide for their children. Low socio-economic status can cause parents to feel stressed and anxious about the future of their children. This can limit their access to resources that may help them. When there is political instability and insecurity in the nation. The Parents becomes so worried about the safety of their wards which can lead to stress and anxiety. Parents stress and anxiety level can increase when there is inadequate social support. Pressure from the society can have a profound impact on parental self-doubt and fear of failure, leading to feelings of inadequacy, anxiety and stress. The following factors can be responsible for the effects of societal pressure on parental self-doubt and fear of failure.

- i. Social comparison - social media can amplify social comparison, leading to negative psychological outcome like low self-esteem and depression, as users are constantly exposed to potentially unrealistic portrayals of others lives. Social comparison is the process of evaluating oneself assessment and self-improvement. It can be upward (company to those perceived as superior), downward (comparing to those perceived as inferior) or lateral (comparing to those perceived as equal). Social media platforms provide a constant stream of information and images, making Social comparison both easier and more frequent. Social media platforms may unconsciously become benchmark. Social media influencers and other prominent figures on these platforms can become benchmarks for success geed aspiration, further fueling social comparison.
- ii. Fear of judgment - Fear of other peoples judgment sometimes can be so overwhelming that we decide to give up on what we want, or on something new and out of ordinary. We refuse to ask more from our lives and leave our comfort zone because our first thoughts are what will they assume about me? Are they going to approve? Am I going to let them down?. Going out of our comfort zone is very scary. We all know, but does staying inside make us feel good Idle can't live our lifes lying to ourselves, If we don't listen to the little voice inside of us, our mind and body will. They tell us that we are going against our genuine desire and aspiration, with powerful emotions and anxiety, or sometimes even psychosomatic symptoms. When we feel that judgment a makes us feel uncomfortable, take a breath all think "why do i feel bad about it? Which emotion am i feeling for now? sadness, rage, fear? What am I afraid of? Why de i need their approval? Having opinions and advice from people is a good thing of course, but judgments can be the destructive if we don't know how to handle them
- iii. Unrealistic expectations – Attempts towards meeting social expectations on perfect parenting can also trigger fear of failure where parent cannot meet these unattainable standards. Parental expectations had a larger impact the parental criticism on self-oriented and other-oriented perfectionism, therefore, parental expectation may be more damaging than parental criticism. Young people internalise those expectations and depend on them for their self- esteem when they fail to meet them, as they invariably will, they will be critical of themselves for not matching up. To compensate for these, they strive to be perfect.
- iv) Mental health - Parents have high expectations for themselves and high expectations for what the children should become. Then, on the flipside, a lot of judgment go on when comparing two people with different personalities. When a child has mental health disorder, parent's report a higher level of burnout and a greater livelihood for them to insult, criticize screenmat, curse at and for physically harm their children (i.e. expected spanking). Higher level of self-reported parental burnout and harsh parenting practices are associated with more mental health problem in children. When parents are burned out, they have more depression, anxiety and stress, but their children also do behaviorally and are emotionally worse.

The Consequences of Perfectionism in Parenting

There are empirical evidence that shows a significant correlation between perfectionism and parental anxiety, depression and burnout, perfectionistic parents tends to experience higher levels of anxiety, as they strive for flawless parenting and worry about making mistake.

Perfectionism has been linked to increase symptom of depression in parents, particularly when they feel they have failed to meet their high standards. Perfectionistic parents are more prone to burnout due to the excessive pressure they put on themselves, leading to emotional exhaustion and decreased motivation.

Children of perfectionistic parents may experience increased pressure, criticism and stress, potentially affecting their self-esteem and well-being, Social media can exacerbate perfectionism by presenting curated image of perfect families, leading to unrealistic comparism, and increased anxiety, Practicing self-compassion, mindfulness, and self-care can help.

The relentless pursuit of perfections can lead to feelings of exhaustion, cynicism, and reduced performance, ultimately contributing to depression and burnout (Malloch & Jackson, 1981). Perfectionism can lead to feelings of guilt and shame when Parent inevitably make mistakes or fail to meet their own expectations (Tardy, 2013). Constant pressure to be perfect can lead to decreased self-esteem and confidence making it more difficult for parents to effectively care for their children (Furedi, 2002). Perfectionism can also lead to strained relationships between parents and their children, and as well as between parents and their partners (Shankoff & Philips, 2000)

Perfectionism can also affect interpersonal relationships. It may have unrealistic expectation of others leading to conflicts and dissatisfaction in relationships. They may also struggle with vulnerability and fear of judgment, making it difficult to

form close, trusting connections. In some cases, perfectionist may isolate themselves to avoid perceived failure or criticism from others.

The stress and anxiety associated with perfectionism can have significant implication for physical health, Chronic stress can weaken the immune system, increase the rate of cardiovascular diseases and contribute to gastrointestinal issues. (Dunkley et al, 2000). Children of perfectionistic parents may internalise their parents' high standards and develop feeling of inadequacy and low self-worth. They may also internalize their parents' perfectionistic tendencies, leading to constant self-doubt and feeling of failure, even when they are doing their best. Perfectionistic parent may become overprotective, feeling that their children will fail or make mistakes, so which can hinder their children's development of independence and resilient.

The fear of not doing things perfectly can lead to procrastination, as children may be demoralized by the pressure to achieve perfection. Children may also experience poorer attachment to relationships with their parents, leading to fear of abandonment. Perfectionism can lead to unhealthy motivation tactics like sharing, and too much praise for abilities instead of nurturing a growth mindset in child.

Excessive pressure on children can have unintended consequence. Rather than motivating them to excel, it can lead to burnout and decline in academic performance. When children feels they never meet their parents expectations, it can erode their motivation and self-esteem, causing them to disengage from the learning process. Furthermore, the pressure to succeed in a specific field can limit their ability to explore their interest and passions, potentially leading to a lack of fulfillment in their future careers. By casing the burden of expectation parents can help their children cultivate a genuine love for learning and a sense of purpose that will benefit them in the long run.

The constant pressure to meet unrealistic expectations can have a profound impacts on a child's mental health, leading to high level of anxiety and stress. This stress can manifest in various ways such as difficulty sleeping, problem with concentration and social withdrawal. Furthermore, excessive parental pressure can contribute to feelings of hopelessness and worthlessness potentially leading to depression. When children feel they cannot meet their parents' expectations, they may develop a sense of inadequacy and low self-esteem. The pursuit of unattainable perfection can become overwhelming, leading to increased stress and anxiety. In some cases excessive pressure related to appearance or achievement can also contribute development of eating disorder and body image issues. Ultimately, children who feel they are constantly falling short may withdraw from social situation, struggling to cope with the weight of expectations can lead to a buildup of frustration and resentment potentially causing anger management problems an aggression.

Consequences of Parental Failure

The fear of failure is a powerful force that drives many individuals to strive for perfection, in the context of parenting. This fear can be particularly deliberating, as parents may feel that their children's futures are dependent on the ability to provide a perfect upbringing. Some perfectionist can be paralysed by the fear of failure without even being able to start the task. These consequence can apply to the greatest achievers of our time, where they have refused to hand in, or present their great work due to fear of failure, and worry that people will judge and criticize them.

On a more damaging note, perfectionism, in its pathological state, can also be considered a risk factor for suicide. With perfectionists being highly self-critical and frequently suffering, anxiety and depression when they do not meet the excessively high standard they placed on themselves, combine with not being able to display to the world how they really feel. It increases the risk of suicide "ideation" Additionally because of their tendency the present themselves, as perfect, they are usually too ashamed to seek help.

The stigma of parental failure is a significant force to seeking help, particularly when it came to addressing mental health issues in children. Many parents worried about being judged or labeled as "bad parents" if they seek help for their children's mental health problems. The fear of stigma can lead to delayed or forgone treatment, exacerbating the child's mental health issue Lack of knowledge about where to seek help and how to access services, Fear of judgment and previous negative experiences may be a banner to seeking help.

Parental failure, or the perception of failure, can have severe and long-lasting consequences for parents, Children, and families. The consequences, of parental failure are a growing concern, as they can impact not only on individual families but also society as a whole. Children of parents who feel they have failed may experience emotional and Psychological distress, depression and low self-esteem. They may act out or engaged in problematic behaviors as a result of the parents perceived failure.(Webster-Straton, 2018) Children may struggle with attachment and forming healthy relationships due to their parents emotional unavailability and inconsistency.

Parent's themselves can suffer severe consequences by having strain relationships between the parents and their children and as well as between their partners. Parents who feel they have failed may experience a loss of identity and purpose,

leading to feeling of emptiness and despair. (Tardy, 2000). Parental failure can have broader consequences for society. There will be increased mental health issues among children and adult placing a strain on mental health resources. It can also have economic implication including increased health care cost and decreased productivity.

The Way Out

Perfectionism might seem like a harmless drive for excellence, but over time, it can come at a huge cost. Emotionally, it can lead to anxiety, depression and burnout. One might feel constantly stressed or overwhelmed always trying to keep up with impossible expectation.

When one is fixated on being perfect socially perfectionism can isolate man. It is hard to let our guard down or show vulnerability. Relationships can suffer because one is afraid to be seen as anything less than flawless. The good news is one doesn't have to stay stuck in the perfectionism cycle. The following are the possible ways to avoid rigidity in perfectionism in order to live healthier. They are:

1. **Accept uncertainty:** - the fear of not being in control is one of the biggest drivers of perfectionism, yet life is full of uncertainty and trying to control everything will only add to stress. Individual should learn to tolerate the unknown and trust that he or she can handle whatever comes his way. Perfectionism might promise success and control, but in reality it often brings stress, frustration, and isolation. It's about recognising that one is enough, flaws and all by embracing imperfection, individuals can find more joy, peace, and fulfilment in our life.
2. **Practice self-compassion** - Individuals should treat him or herself with the same kindness and understanding he or she would offer to someone else. He should be kind to himself, when one catches himself slipping into perfectionist thinking he should pause and ask himself whether he would speak to a friend in that way?
3. **Challenge your Beliefs** - Begin by questioning the idea that your worth is tied to your achievements. What would happen if you made a mistake? Would the world fall apart? Probably not. Practice giving your self-permission to be imperfect. Perfectionism thrives on the belief that mistakes are how we grow they are not a reflection of your worth.
4. **Practice mindfulness** - When anxiety or panic hits, mindfulness can help a person to manage intense emotions. The following technique could be of great assistance:
To calm your mind and body, start by practicing slow, deep breathing to soothe your nervous system. Next, tense and release each major muscle group to ease physical tension, allowing your body to relax. Take a moment to notice the sights, sounds, smells, and texture around you grounding yourself in the present. Feel your feet firmly on the ground connecting with the earth beneath you. Finally, visualize a peaceful place, perhaps a serene beach or a tranquil forest and let its calming atmosphere wash over you, calming your mood.
5. **Set realistic and flexible goals** - Being a perfectionist often involves extremely high standards, which can lead to disappointment and stress. Instead, set realistic, achievable goals that allow for flexibility. Break large tasks into smaller, manageable steps and adjust your goals as needed.
6. **View mistakes as learning opportunities** - Mistakes are a natural part of growth and learning instead of seeing them as failures, view them as an opportunity to learn and improve, treat yourself with the same kindness you would offer a friend, acknowledge your effort, recognise everyone has limitations, and be gentle with yourself when things don't go as planned.
7. **Avoid comparison** - constantly comparing yourself to others can fuel perfectionism. Remember, everyone's journey is unique, and what you see on the surface doesn't reflect the whole story. Focus on your own progress and growth rather than trying to measure up to others. If social media makes you envious, reflect in your own achievements and the progress you have made in your personal journey.
8. **Set boundaries** - Perfectionists can over commit, trying to excel in all areas of life. Learn to set boundaries and prioritise what's truly important. It's alright to say no to additional tasks or commitments. Focusing on the big picture can direct your energy more effectively and go a long way in overcoming perfectionism.
9. **Get Support** - Dealing with perfectionism can be tough on your own. Therapy for perfectionism can help you address underlying issues and develop healthier coping strategies. Support groups of friends who understand your struggles, can also offer valuable perspective and encouragement.
10. **Embrace "Good Enough"** - Let go of the need for everything to be perfect. Sometimes, "good enough" really is enough. Perfectionist often spend hours tweaking and refusing things that are already fine. Learn to recognise when you have done a solid job and move on.

Conclusion

The phenomenon of parental failure in the age of perfectionism is a complex and multifaceted issue, influenced by a myriad of cultural and societal factors. This examination has endeavoured to unravel the intricate web of expectations, pressures and norms that contribute to the pervasive sense of inadequacy and failure among parents. The Cultural factors that contribute to this phenomenon are far reaching and insidious. Social media platforms, celebrity parenting, expert parenting advices, and traditional and cultural values all converge to create an unattainable deal of perfect parenting. Cultural factors perpetuate unrealistic expectations fueling the fear of failure and the pressure to conform to societal norms. Societal factors, including societal expectation, social media parenting styles and trends can further exacerbate the phenomenon of parental failure. The emphasis on academic achievement, the pressure to be involved on Children's education, and the commercialisation of parenting all contribute to the sense of overwhelm and inadequacy that many parents experience.

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